

Emotion Through Breath in the ACT UP Oral History Project

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Abstract

This paper explores how computational analysis of paralinguistic cues, particularly breathing, can enrich the study of emotionality in Oral History Archives (OHA). While oral historians recognise the loss of non-verbal information in transcript-based research, large-scale audio analysis remains underdeveloped. Using the Voices of ACT UP (VO-ACTUP) dataset, which contains interviews with ACT UP activists about their experiences during the AIDS epidemic, we investigate how non-verbal audio features capture emotional nuances that transcripts cannot convey. To support this analysis, we implement and extend state-of-the-art speech-based breathing prediction models using the UCL-SBM dataset and propose two new WavLM-based architectures that improve current performance. We then assess robustness by aligning predicted breathing signals with annotated breathing events in VO-ACTUP. Finally, we examine how breathing-derived features, such as breathing rate, correlate with emotional expression across the corpus. Our work demonstrates the potential of breathing analysis to reveal affective dimensions of oral history at scale.

Oral history has always been shaped (and constrained) by the technologies available to record, preserve, and analyse it. As Michael Frisch argues in [1], each technological shift has fundamentally altered how scholars approach oral history archives (OHA). The transition from analogue tapes to digital files, and from manual transcription to automatic speech recognition (ASR) and natural language processing (NLP), has opened new possibilities for accessing and navigating large collections of interviews [2, 3, 4].

Even though oral historians are aware of the inherent loss of non-verbal information, such as gestures and rhythm, occurring when relying solely on transcripts, the lack of tools and resources for large-scale analysis of audio and video has left these modalities largely understudied [1, 5, 6]. In audio, voices convey meaning through tone, emphasis, pauses, laughter, and, for example, sarcasm—information that disappears when looking only at text [7]. As McHugh notes, the interview is a “performance in search of text,” and reading the transcript alone means missing the performance itself [8]. This performative dimension can provide insight into the speaker, reveal how past events are remembered and narrated in the present, and highlight the emotional components shaping the testimony [9]. As a result, while ASR and NLP have expanded access to oral history archives, they have also inadvertently reinforced a text-centric view that loses the “voice” of the interview.

For this reason, Smyth et al. have argued for a “sound as data” approach to Oral History, encouraging researchers to apply analytical and interpretative strategies traditionally reserved for text to audiovisual material [10]. Yet few scientific works have attempted to study emotionality in OHA using computational methods [11, 12]. In this work, we explore how computational analysis of non-verbal audio cues (i.e. “how things are said”) offers a promising way to examine the emotional complexity present in OHA.

Inspired by the work of Salah et al. [13], who showed that changes in breathing can highlight emotionally charged moments in archival recordings, we focus on breathing as a meaningful element of the audio signal. Emotional states are accompanied by physiological changes throughout the body, including changes in breathing, making it a subtle yet meaningful indicator of affect. Research shows that high-arousal negative emotions such as anger or stress increase respiratory rate and depth, while sadness or depression tend to be associated with slow and shallow breathing. These findings suggest that breathing patterns, similar to other paralinguistic audio-cues, can carry emotional information that is not always accessible in the verbal content of speech [14, 15].

To address the research question, “How can paralinguistics and breathing-signal-derived insights support humanities research in oral history (OH) archives?”, we build on the dataset introduced by Pessanha et al. [16]. This dataset, “Voices of ACT UP” (VO-ACTUP), contains 728 manually annotated samples from emotionally charged interviews, where the perceived emotionality of speech was labelled using four categories: “happiness,” “sadness,” “anger,” and “neutral.” In their paper, the authors introduce the use of this reduced annotation scheme, based on Ekman’s basic emotions [17], as a starting point for identifying emotionally salient sections of the interviews. They also provide, for each emotion category, a set of emotions included under its label to improve consistency and shared understanding among annotators. The interviews focus on the AIDS Coalition to Unleash Power (ACT UP) Oral History Project, which documents the group’s public activism. ACT UP testimonies reflect complex emotions such as fear, grief, and what curator Jim Hubbard calls the activists’ “*righteous anger*” [18]. The findings of Pessanha et al. [16] demonstrate that paralinguistic features capture emotional nuance more effectively than text alone and reflect the inherent ambiguity of emotion in speech. Their results provide a good foundation for further studies using VO-ACTUP to explore emotion, particularly through paralinguistic cues.

Speech production and breathing are deeply intertwined, making manual annotation of breathing events during speech particularly challenging [19]. Breathing belts, which track thoracic or abdominal movement, have proven useful for studying speech–breathing relationships [20, 21]. Using datasets that contain both speech and a ground-truth breathing signal, it is possible to train breathing signal prediction models, allowing researchers to analyse breathing patterns from any speech recording, without the need for specialised hardware or, in our case, to analyse breathing in data already collected.

To further improve speech-based breathing prediction, we used the UCL-SBM dataset [20], which provides aligned speech and breathing signals collected with respiratory belts. We implement previously proposed state-of-the-art (SOTA) methods [22, 23, 24], explicitly stating any assumptions or adjustments made during their implementation. We then introduce extensions to improve their performance and propose two novel WavLM-based architectures, surpassing the current SOTA [25]. All models are evaluated on the publicly available UCL-SBM dataset to ensure reproducibility and fair comparison. This work provides a systematic benchmark for speech-based breathing prediction and supports more reliable analysis of breathing patterns in speech. To evaluate the robustness of these models in a cross-dataset setting, we will evaluate the alignment of the predicted breathing signals in the VO-ACTUP dataset with manually annotated breathing events to evaluate the model’s robustness.

Finally, after establishing robust breathing-signal prediction models, we aim to investigate how features derived from these signals, such as breathing rate, correlate with emotional expression in the VO-ACTUP dataset. Based on the obtained results, we plan to use these features for automatic emotion assessment across the entire ACT UP Oral History Project collection. Possible applications for our proposed approach are tracking emotional flow across long interviews, identifying emotionally salient moments, and analysing community-specific responses, in this case through the lens of activists, to different events and movements through the AIDS epidemic. The narratives of oral history are often nuanced, especially when looking at sensitive interviews such as the ACT UP Oral History Project; hence, such tools might reveal sentiments not contained in the text, and offer a more complete interpretation of these personal stories.

In conclusion, similar to what happened upon the introduction of ASR and NLP into the field, we argue that the study of paralinguistic cues, including breathing, has the potential to open up new dimensions of meaning and bring the “voices” back to large scale archival studies, currently not accessible through manual analysis or text alone.

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